

Polarographic Study of Metal Ion Complexes with Keratin Fibres (Wool) at pH 4-5 and Temp. 30°. Part I. Chlorides and Nitrates of Hg⁺⁺, Cu⁺⁺, Cd⁺⁺ and Pb⁺⁺

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Study of the reaction of various metal ions Hg⁺⁺, Cu⁺⁺, Cd⁺⁺ and Pb⁺⁺ from the aqueous solutions of their nitrates and chlorides of various concentrations (0.0125 to 0.0625M) at pH 4-5 and temp. 30° with sheep wool respectively, has been made by analysing polarographically after diluting forty times (1) the equilibrium solutions and (2) 0.2M NaCl extracts of the treated wool after washing with distilled and CO₂-free water in case of (i) pure wool, (ii) benzoquinone treated, (iii) methanol esterified, (iv) reduced with Na₂SO₃+urea, and (v) deaminated with NaNO₂+HAC. The reaction was very slow at conc. 0.0125M, but in case of higher conc. (0.025 to 0.0625M) it got completed in 8 to 84 hours. From the differences in initial and final conc., the amount of the metal in gum-atoms combined with one gum. mole of wool has been calculated, which varied with the treatment. From the results, the sites of reaction with HgCl₂ molecules and the above-mentioned metal ions, in the molecule of wool, have been discussed; the number of ions exchanged on treatment with 0.2M NaCl, has been considered to be adsorbed on the surface of the keratin fibres.

Keratin fibres such as sheep wool and other animal hair consist almost of proteins, established by relatively frequent primary and secondary valence cross-links (salt and disulphide linkages) between neighbouring polypeptide chains. Speakman and Coke¹ found from gravimetric estimation of Hg(1c) in equilibrium solutions in presence of 0.1N HCl that HgCl₂ was absorbed strongly by amino groups of side chains and also that no attack on the disulphide bond occurred at 25°. Speakman and Peill² studied the reaction between wool and benzoquinone; they showed that the maximum reaction occurred with -NH₂ groups in pH range 4-6. Leach³ studied polarographically the reaction of HgCl₂ with sheep wool at different pH 1-6, using 4x10⁻⁴ M solution, but he could not complete the reaction (perhaps due to low concentration, according to the authors). He observed that methanol-esterified wool took up the same amount of HgCl₂ as the unesterified, proving no combination with -COOH; on reduction with Na₂SO₃+urea at pH 8, more HgCl₂ was taken up due to production of -SH binding sites by reversible splitting of -S-S-bonds. He also observed that on addition of arginine to the reaction mixture, no change in the uptake of HgCl₂ occurred, from which he concluded that there is no reaction of HgCl₂ with -NH₂ groups of side chains, as suggested by Speakman and Coke (*loc. cit.*). Pfrankuch and Hagenguth⁴ concluded from polarographic studies that Mn⁺⁺, Cu⁺⁺, Fe⁺⁺, Ag⁺⁺ ions could be bound up with proteins and viruses. Tanford⁵ showed that the depression of the polarographic diffusion current of cadmium by bovine serum albumin was due to the complex

1. Speakman and Coke, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1939, 35, 246.
2. Speakman and Peill, *J. Textile Inst.*, 1943, 34, 70T.
3. Leach, *Austr. J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 13, 547-66.
4. Pfrankuch and Hagenguth, *Biochem. Z.*, 1942, 313, 1-10.
5. Tanford, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 2066-70.

formation between Cd and the protein. Narwani and Gursahani⁶ succeeded in extracting HgCl_2 adsorbed on wool by treating with 0.2N NaCl solution.

The object of the present work was to compare the action of $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, HgCl_2 , $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, CdCl_2 , $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, CuCl_2 , $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and PbCl_2 at various concentrations on sheep wool, at its isoelectric point pH 4.5, by determining the concentration of the respective metal ions polarographically in (i) the equilibrium solutions and (ii) NaCl extracts. The adsorbent systems consisted of (1) pure wool, (2) wool which was benzoquinonetreated to protect $-\text{NH}_2$, $-\text{CONH}_2$, $-\text{CO}-\text{NH}-$ and $-\text{SH}$ groups, (3) methanol-esterified wool, (4) wool treated with $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{urea}$ at pH 8.0 to reduce $-\text{S}-\text{S}-$ to $-\text{2SH}$, and (5) wool deaminated with $\text{NaNO}_2 + \text{HAC}$ at pH 3-4. The above mentioned salts have been chosen for the reactions because they are either used as insecticides or have application for mineral dyeing of wool: $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ is used for carroting or felting of wool.

EXPERIMENTAL

Long staple, yellowish wool of Australian sheep of the same species was first washed in running water to remove suspended impurities, then with ethyl alcohol to remove grease and finally with distilled water repeatedly; it was dried in vacuum desiccator.

0.25 g of pure dry wool was treated in an air thermostat at $30^\circ \pm 1^\circ$ with 25 ml, of 0.0125, 0.025, 0.0375, 0.050 and 0.0625 M solutions of HgCl_2 , CdCl_2 , CuCl_2 and PbCl_2 in presence of very dilute HCl at pH 4-5 and $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in presence of very dilute HNO_3 at pH 4-5. In case of $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, the colour of wool changed to deep reddishbrown. The completion of the reaction, as determined, from the polarographic analysis of the equilibrium solutions, took 8 to 84 hours, depending upon the concentrations and nature of the solution, as shown in Table III. At 0.0125 M, the lowest concentration used, the reaction was not completed even in 84 hours. The order of reaction in all cases was calculated according to the procedure of van't Hoff differential equation, and was found to be 2.0 (data not given).

After pipetting out 12.5 ml of the equilibrium solution in a 500 ml measuring flask (1), the wool residue was washed with CO_2 -free distilled water repeatedly till the washings were free from the metal ions; the washings were collected in a 500 ml measuring flask (2) and the volumes of both (1) & (2) were made up to the mark after the required amount of supporting electrolyte and 5 ml of 1% gelatin solution (suppressor) were added. As suggested by Miller and Kolthoff⁷, 0.1N KNO_3 for HgCl_2 and 0.1N HNO_3 for $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, while 1.0 N HCl and 1.0 N HNO_3 for other chlorides and nitrates respectively, were used as supporting electrolytes. The equilibrium solutions were analysed polarographically, using Lange manual polarometer, multiflex galvanometer and dropping Hg electrode versus satd. calomel electrode. The pH of initial and equilibrium solutions before dilution were determined by means of Cambridge pH meter.

The treated wool after being washed with CO_2 -free distilled water was kept in 50 ml of 0.2N NaCl for 24 hours. It was then washed repeatedly with CO_2 -free distilled water into a 100 ml measuring flask and the volume made up to the mark after adding 1 ml of 1% gelatin solution. The solution was analysed polarographically for the metal ions exchanged with Na^+ ions. The treated wool samples were similarly analysed.

6. Narwani and Gursahani, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 527.

7. Miller and Kolthoff, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 1013.

Method of calculating the amount of the metal combined with 0.25 g. of wool: From polarographic analysis of the initial and final concentration, the number of g. atoms of each metal ion combined with one g. mole of wool was calculated, taking 59,000 as the mol. wt. of the wool. The results obtained at 0.0625 M salts are summarised as typical in Table I for the sample of pure wool, and in Table II for the treated wools. The values of the polarographic factor F, obtained from the equation $F=id_0/C$ used in calculating concentrations C were 1487, 2876, 3032, 4034, 1662, 3203, 3169 and 4457 for $Hg(NO_3)_2$, $Cd(NO_3)_2$, $Pb(NO_3)_2$, $Cu(NO_3)_2$, $HgCl_2$, $CdCl_2$, $PbCl_2$, and $CuCl_2$ respectively.

In order to prove that $HgCl_2$ combines in molecular form and the others as ions with the amido groups in the molecule of wool, the polarographic study was carried out of the interaction of the salts with asparagin ($HOOC$, $CH(NH_2)$, CH_2 , $CONH_2$, H_2O) for this purpose, 0.094 g of asparagin was added to 25 ml of 0.0625 M solution of the metal salts and the mixture kept for 72 hours in an air thermostat at $30^\circ \pm 1^\circ$. The equilibrium solution was diluted and analysed polarographically in the same manner as described above; the results are shown in Table IV.

TABLE I
Polarographic analysis of equilibrium solutions of 0.0625 M metal salts in contact with pure wool.

Salt	E_d Volts	Initial pH	Initial conc. $id_0(\mu A)$	Final pH	Final conc. $id(\mu A)$	id_0/id (μA)	No. of g. atoms combined with one g. mole of pure wool
$HgCl_2$	+0.22	4.52	2.60	3.80	1.72	0.88	125
$Hg(NO_3)_2$	+0.22	4.32	2.93	4.10	1.80	0.53	84
$Cd(NO_3)_2$	-0.60	5.00	4.40	4.49	3.47	0.93	78
$CdCl_2$	-0.62	5.00	5.00	4.50	3.95	1.05	77
$Pb(NO_3)_2$	-0.44	4.30	4.80	3.80	3.80	1.00	77
$PbCl_2$	-0.42	4.40	5.00	3.90	3.95	1.05	77
$Cu(NO_3)_2$	-0.01	4.80	6.30	4.94	5.00	1.30	76
$CuCl_2$	-0.22	4.80	7.00	4.34	5.55	1.46	76

TABLE II
Polarographic analysis of equilibrium solutions of 0.0625 M metal salts in contact with treated wool.

Salt	Esterified		Deaminated		Reduced No. of g. atoms combined/ g. mole of wool.	Benzo- quinone treated No. of g. atom combined/ g. mole of of wool.	Benzoquin- one treat- ed reaction in presence of 0.2 M NaCl.
	No. of g. atom combined/ g. mole of wool.	Decrease in pH	No. of g. atoms combined/ g. mole of wool.	Decrease in pH			
$HgCl_2$	125	0.72	75	0.68	183	20	0.0
$Hg(NO_3)_2$	83	0.42	84	0.42	83	20	0.0
$Cd(NO_3)_2$	78	0.51	48	0.50	137	20	0.0
$CdCl_2$	77	0.50	48	0.50	137	20	0.0
$Pb(NO_3)_2$	78	0.50	48	0.48	138	20	0.0
$PbCl_2$	77	0.50	48	0.49	137	20	0.0
$Cu(NO_3)_2$	77	0.48	48	0.46	136	20	0.0
$CuCl_2$	76	0.48	48	0.46	136	20	0.0

TABLE III

Approximate time (hours) required for completion of the reaction of 0.25 g of pure wool with 25 ml solutions of the following salts.

Conc. in g. mole/lit	Hg (NO ₃) ₂	Hg Cl ₂	Time in hours				
			Cd (NO ₃) ₂	Cd Cl ₂	Pb (NO ₃) ₂	Cu(NO ₃) ₂	CuCl ₂
0.0250	50	50	72	72	84	60	60
0.0375	50	50	72	72	72	60	60
0.0500	16	16	50	36	50	36	36
0.0625	16	8	24	36	16	16	36

TABLE IV

Polarographic results for equilibrium solution of 0.0625M metal salts in contact with asparagin. Calculated for anhydrous asparagin; wt.=0.084 g; Mol. wt.=132.14 g.

Salt	E _d Volt	Initial conc. id ₀ (μA)	Initial pH	Final conc. id (μA)	Final pH	id-id (μA)	g. atom of metal comb. with one g. mole of asparagin.
Hg. Cl ₂	+0.22	2.60	4.52	1.60	4.52	1.00	0.94
Hg (NO ₃) ₂	+0.22	2.33	4.50	1.83	4.02	0.48	0.50
Cd (NO ₃) ₂	-0.60	4.40	5.00	3.52	4.44	0.88	0.49
Cd Cl ₂	-0.62	5.00	5.00	4.00	4.40	1.00	0.49
Pb (NO ₃) ₂	-0.44	4.80	4.80	3.84	3.90	0.96	0.50
Pb Cl ₂	-0.42	5.00	4.40	4.00	4.00	1.00	0.49
Cu(NO ₃) ₂	-0.01	6.30	4.60	5.04	4.10	1.26	0.49
Cu Cl ₂	-0.22	7.00	4.50	5.56	4.00	1.44	0.50

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

From the results of the benzoquinone-treated wool in Table II and ion exchange experiments with 0.2N NaCl, the authors observed that at pH 4-5, 19 to 20 g. moles of HgCl₂ (Hg⁺⁺ ions being absent in aqueous solution as HgCl₂ is covalent) and same number of g.atoms of the metal ions in other salts, get adsorbed on surface of one g.mole of wool, all the possible reacting groups, -SH, -CONH₂, and -CO-NH- are protected by benzoquinone, the first two⁸ by chemical reaction and the third by polymerisation forming a resin on the keratin fibre⁹. Table I shows the number of g.atoms of various metals combined with one g.mole of pure wool (59000 g) as determined from the depression in polarographic diffusion current on completion of the reaction of untreated wool with 0.0625M solution of each of them at pH 4-5 (isoelectric pH of wool being nearly 4.5 as determined by Sookne and Harris¹⁰ by streaming potential method) and at temp. 30° ± 1°. The decrease in pH given in Table I of isoelectric wool¹⁰ in presence of salts, suggests combination of metal ions with such groups of the keratin molecules as contain

8. Alexander and Hudson, "Physics and Chemistry of Wool".

9. Stoves, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1943, 39, 301.

10. Sookne and Harris, *J. Res. N. B. S.*, 1941, 26, 65.

replaceable H. It has been indicated earlier that the primary amino and $-\text{COOH}$ groups are not involved in combination since there is no change in the amount of the metal combined on addition of arginine and esterification of wool with methanol respectively. The data in Table IV which shows no change in pH with HgCl_2 added to asparagin (an amide of aspartic acid) confirm that HgCl_2 does not combine by displacement of H but co-ordinates with $-\text{NH}_2$ of amido group, whereas the other ions do and displace H ions as lowering in pH indicates. The figures in the last column of Table IV further show that one bivalent ion combines with two molecules of asparagin.

Again Table I shows that there is decrease in pH on addition of HgCl_2 to wool and Table II shows decrease in combination on deamination. This is also true for the other ions studied, suggesting that in addition to coordination with the amido groups, there is combination at certain other groups having replaceable H. According to Speakman and Coke¹ and Leach², $-\text{NH}-$ group of (i) side chain such as that in histidine residues containing imidazole group, and (ii) peptide linkages, are the possible sites for combination of HgCl_2 molecules and other metal ions. But according to Tanford³, $-\text{NH}-$ of histidine residue dissociates at pH 6.8; therefore at pH 4-5, only $-\text{NH}-$ of peptide linkages is the alternative possible site.

Considering the results given in Table II for the esterified, deaminated, reduced and benzoquinone-treated wool respectively and deducting 20 adsorbed g. atoms from the total number combined with one g. mole of wool, given in Table I, we get 105, 64, 58, 57, 57, 57, 56 and 56 g. atoms for HgCl_2 , $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, CdCl_2 , $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, PbCl_2 , $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, and CuCl_2 , respectively combining with one g. mole of pure wool. The metal ions of all other salts excepting HgCl_2 and $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, are thus found to combine to the same extent perhaps with $-\text{CONH}_2$ and $-\text{CO-NH}-$ groups.

In case of HgCl_2 , the difference between the number of g. atoms combined with one g. mole of pure (or esterified) and deaminated wool is 50, which is expected to be complexed in molecular form with $-\text{CONH}_2$ groups; on deducting 20 adsorbed atoms from 75 combined with deaminated wool, there remain 55 combined in molecular form with $-\text{CO-NH}-$ groups. According to the figures given in Astbury's table, there are 48 $-\text{CONH}_2$, 56 $-\text{CO-NH}-$, 58 $-\text{S-S}-$, and 12 $-\text{OH}$ (phenolic of tyrosene residues) in one molecule of wool. So out of a total of 105 molecules HgCl_2 cocombined, 48 are accounted for (within experimental error) $-\text{CONH}_2$ and 56 for $-\text{CO-NH}-$ groups. It is observed that there is nearly the same decrease in pH in case of deaminated (Table II) as in pure wool (Table I). It is concluded that combination with $-\text{CO-NH}-$ is accompanied by displacement of one H by one mole of HgCl_2 , perhaps forming $-\text{N}(\text{HgCl})-\text{CO}-$ and HCl . There being an increase of 58 g. atoms in combination after reduction of wool, it is confirmed that there are 58 $-\text{S-S}-$ groups in one molecule of pure wool, giving 116 $-\text{SH}$ groups on reduction, each H of which is replaced by 1/2 Hg atom forming 58 $-\text{S-Hg-S}-$ and 116 HCl .

In case of $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, 64 g. atoms (84-20) of Hg combined with one g. mole of pure wool, 58 combine with 58 $-\text{S-S}-$ forming $-\text{S-Hg-S}-$ and 6 with 12 $-\text{OH}$ (phenolic); Millon's reaction indicates phenolic $-\text{OH}$. There is no increase in combination on reduction of wool. The decrease in pH may be attributed to replacement of 2H of 2 $-\text{OH}$ (phenolic) groups by one Hg(ic) atom; the decrease is less, because there is no combination with $-\text{CO-NH}-$ or $-\text{CONH}_2$ groups. On deamination, there is no decrease in the number of combined atoms.

In case of nitrates and chlorides of Cd, Pb, and Cu(II), (1) the total combination, (2) the decrease on deamination, (3) the increase on reduction, and (4) the decrease in pH are nearly the same. Thus out of 57 to 58 combined with pure wool (Table I), 24 g. atom combined with 48 $-CONH_2$ groups, 28 with 56 $-CO.NH-$ groups and the remaining 6 may be combining with 12 $-OH$ (phenolic) of tyrosene residues.

From the observed second order rate of reaction, it is suggested that one keratin molecule reacts with one bivalent metal ion followed by another reaction in which a second molecule of keratin combines with the metal keratin species formed initially.

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